

DIFFERENTIATED LESSON PLANNING IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article talks about teaching a foreign language as a second language, as well as organizing a differentiated lesson in this process.*

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Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, i.e. in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in our time when international relations are on the rise. Pupils and students studying in our country usually study three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. The mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When talking about the second language, it is considered as the language of relatives and neighbors who are representatives of other nations.

A foreign language is the language of a foreign country. Western European languages (English, Spanish, German, French) and Eastern languages (Arabic, Turkish, Persian, Chinese, Indian) are taught in our republic. These languages are included in the curricula of educational institutions. The process of teaching all three languages is different. The mother tongue and the second language are learned in a natural situation, and a foreign language is learned in an artificial environment. Communication in a foreign language mainly takes place in the classroom under the guidance of the teacher. Among the three languages, learning and teaching a foreign language differs sharply in certain aspects. This, in turn, requires the use of appropriate foreign language teaching technology. By carefully mastering the achievements of the methodical science, the foreign language teacher will be able to clearly know the standard of language experience of the student and to improve it further. Effective teaching of foreign languages requires knowledge of its methodology. Learning and teaching foreign languages largely depends on the theoretical development of foreign language teaching methodology issues and the creative application of theory in practice.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted teaching, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology.

The methodology of teaching foreign languages is one of the most important factors as the main task of general education schools. This issue is at the center of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic. There are all conditions for educating students of general education schools and for them to master foreign languages. Specialists are doing great work in the field of

teaching foreign languages. Educational programs have been created for all classes. Pedagogical technologies are being created in order to demonstrate knowledge, skills, and abilities in students. Therefore, the foreign language lesson differs from other educational subjects in two aspects, that is, the purpose and content of the lesson. If the foreign language teacher is able to plan the lesson and the types of lessons, as well as plan the foreign language lesson and organize the lesson in accordance with the requirements of the time and the purpose of the lesson, the effectiveness of the lesson and the final result are guaranteed. When planning a foreign language lesson, it is better to plan the organization of a foreign language lesson at the initial stage of foreign language teaching, to plan the lesson taking into account the knowledge levels of the students in the class, to form the conditions of teaching, psychological laws, and speech skills. It is necessary to be informed, to pay attention to knowing the main requirements for modern foreign language classes.

The difficulty of a foreign language is taken into account by the author of the textbook when creating exercises. When the teacher prepares for the educational material of this lesson, he analyzes the comparison of native language and foreign language phenomena. He increases his attention to those small language units, and if necessary, introduces additional exercises. Ensuring a sequence of exercises. Taking into account the skills and qualifications of the students that have been formed so far, determining the order of exercises to be performed in the lesson will give a result. With the intention of incorporating the presented and previously learned educational language material into the composition of skills and qualifications, three-stage - formative, developing and improving exercises are recommended. The teacher carefully integrates the requirements and material of the exercises of the lesson. From the textbook and the exercises given by him, the most effective method of execution is developed. Choosing equipment for the lesson. During the preparation for the lesson, special attention is paid to the choice of educational tools. Sufficient and necessary equipment is prepared depending on the purpose of the lesson, new material, exercises and the level of students. Technical and simple, educational methodical complex and hand-made audiovisual tools and methods of using them are thought out. The behavior and actions of the teacher and students are carefully thought out in preparation for the lesson. The teacher should have professional pedagogical skills (planning, research, organization and training), methodical skills (knowledge of learning language, mastery theory, age and personality characteristics of students). Having mastered planning skills, the teacher will be able to choose language materials, teach, interact with students, and organize the lesson.

Proper planning of the educational process is of great importance in the realization of the goals of learning a foreign language. Planning is the key to successful implementation of all subjects studied in secondary schools, including foreign language teaching. Regardless of the type of plan (lesson plan, thematic, calendar or final), it requires the study of the educational material for a certain period based on all psychological and methodical laws and principles, and the relevant skills and competencies. refers to cultivation. Planning involves several interrelated steps. Accordingly, it is possible to distinguish between an annual plan, a thematic plan and a simple lesson plan. The annual plan is drawn up by the textbook authors. In turn, it is divided into half-yearly and quarterly plans. It defines the topics to be studied. The hours of lessons allocated for teaching each subject are taken into account, the scope of knowledge, the level of growth of speech forms, and the time of the types of inspections. It should be noted that any annual plan should be prepared on the basis of good preparation. If for any reason changes are made to the plan, they should be reflected in the half-yearly and quarterly plans. The process of teaching a foreign language is considered a creative process, and the teacher can make changes to it if necessary. The

main task of thematic planning is to determine the final goal to be achieved as a result of studying a certain topic.

The following steps are necessary for lesson planning in teaching a foreign language as a second language:

1. Determine the objective: Create an understanding of the objective and requirements of the lesson. This will determine how much you want your students to master.

2. Think: Analyze the lessons that students have learned successfully and think about what methods to support in the process of teaching a foreign language.

3. Create the content: Determine the content-elements that are present in the teaching of a foreign language. Structural elements such as grammar, vocabulary, texts and indicators should be planned.

4. Define the types of exercises: Define speaking, writing, listening and processing exercises. You can help students develop practical skills through these types of exercises.

5. Organize evaluation: At the end of the lesson, organize an evaluation system for students to evaluate themselves and test the knowledge they have learned.

6. Make resources mobile: Find books, e-lessons, audio-visual aids, and web-based resources to help you learn a foreign language to increase student interest.

7. Plan the lesson: Organize the lesson by determining the content, type of exercise, duration of the lesson and the learning process of the lesson. Arrange the topics that are the appropriate length of each part and the focus of the study.

8. Increase practice: Organize practical exercises on the lesson and ensure student mastery. Practical exercises will help students develop a foreign language.

9. Evaluate: At the end of the lesson, you need to get students' grades and reflect on the lesson process. This will give you information that you can use to improve and develop your next lessons.

The most important part of teaching a foreign language as a second language is that the training center is well prepared in the lesson planning process. Lessons based on this arrangement help to increase motivation and progress in students.

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